

HIGH PERFORMANCE MATERIALS FOR SEVERE ENVIRONMENTS IN THE FIELD OF AEROSPACE AND POWER GENERATOR TECHNOLOGIES IN JAPAN

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ABSTRACT

Various significant projects which are scheduled for realization in the beginning of the 21st century are now underway, such as space planes, supersonic transports (SST) and hypersonic transports (HST) in the field of aerospace and coal gasification power generation systems and nuclear fusion reactors in the field of new energy. These all projects require the research and development of structural materials with high performance properties which cannot be achieved by conventional materials such as superlative specific strength, stiffness, and resistances to thermal shocks, thermal fatigue and oxidation. In particular, the development of lightweight structural materials capable of withstanding temperatures as high as 1000~2000°C for use in space plane airframe and engine components, gas turbine blade and nuclear reactor walls are required.

The most interesting candidates as advanced structural materials in the field of aeronautic and aerospace technologies are summarized in Figure 1. The hatched areas show currently utilizable temperature ranges and dotted areas are those expected to be developed by the beginning of the 21st century. As shown, few lightweight, heat resistant materials are available in the range of 500~1000°C and above 1500°C. The former range is currently covered by superalloys. New materials for use in this range will be requested to have specific strength and specific creep strength superior to those of superalloys. Ceramics, ceramic matrix composites(CMCs) and carbon/carbon composites(C/Cs) are candidates for the range above 1200°C. Ceramics and CMCs have the advantage of low oxidation damage, which is a critical problem with current super heat-resistant light-weight C/C composite materials. Functionally gradient materials(FGMs) have the benefit of possible thermal stress relaxation effect to compensate for temperature difference through the thickness direction of components. The improvement of heat resistance of composite materials is also possible through the upgrading of material designs and fabrication technology, and much effort is being made in that direction. However, development of other innovative materials is also needed to achieve greater heat resistance for a goal of the future.

In this paper, current R&D trends of advanced structural materials in Japan are first outlined in the field of aerospace and power generator technologies. Secondly, current activities are briefly introduced by focusing on the following related national R&D projects, especially high performance materials for severe environments.

- (1)Research and Development Program on Basic Technologies for Future Industries
 - High Performance Materials for Severe Environments (FY1989-1996) -
 - Fine Ceramics (FY1981-1992) -
- (2)The National Research and Development Program (Large-Scale Project)
 - Super/Hyper-Sonic Transport Propulsion System (FY1989-1996) -

(3)Development of New Energy - Energy Conversion and Storage -
 - Ceramic Gas Turbines (FY1988-1996) -

Finally, some hot topics are presented in fracture mechanics characterization of high performance materials for severe environments because it is the most important and urgent problems to characterize the damage tolerance behavior for a wide use of these advanced materials for primary structural applications. Some technical issues to be solved are also discussed in the development and standardization of testing and evaluation methodologies at ultra-high temperatures.

Keywords: High Performance Materials, National R&D Projects, Intermetallic Compounds, Inter-metallic Compounds Matrix Composites, Carbon/Carbon Composites, Oxidation Resistant Coating Technology, Actual Environment Tests.

Figure 1. Expected temperature capability of advanced structural materials.

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